

Chemical composition and antimicrobial activity of essential oil of *Verbena rigida* Spreng.

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Abstract

The study was planned to determine the chemical composition and antimicrobial properties of the essential oil of *Verbena rigida* Spreng. cultivated in Egypt. The essential oil from aerial parts of *Verbena rigida* Spreng. was prepared by hydrodistillation in a yield of 0.26 % v/w. The chemical composition of the essential oil has been elucidated by gas chromatography-mass spectroscopy analysis. The prepared essential oil was tested against selected species of Gram-positive, Gram-negative bacteria and *Candida* species using disc diffusion method and MICs were determined using broth micro-dilution method. Twenty-eight compounds were identified in the essential oil of *Verbena rigida*, the major components were isobornyl formate (35.2%) and citral (32.9%). The essential oil showed significant antimicrobial activities against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* with MIC 25 µg/mL for *E. coli* and 50 µg/mL for other sensitive bacteria. This is the first study of the chemical composition and antimicrobial activity of the essential oil of *V. rigida*, it proved that the essential oil of *V. rigida* possesses potential antimicrobial properties and could in the future represent a new source of natural antiseptic agents.

Keywords: *Verbena rigida*; Isobornyl formate; Citral; Antimicrobial; Essential oil

1. Introduction

Despite remarkable progress made in medicine, transmissible diseases caused by bacteria, fungi, viruses, and parasites remain major health threats globally. Their impacts are chiefly massive in developing countries where there is extensive unavailability of modern medicines and a high rate of development of drug resistance [1]. The emergence of drug resistance, as well as lack of availability of certain antibiotics, must lead to the search of new antimicrobial agents mainly from natural sources with the goal to discover new chemical agents, which overcome these problems [2]. Current research on naturally occurring compounds and products chiefly focus on plants since they are locally available, less costly, and can be chosen based on existing ethnomedicinal claims for their uses [3].

Several *Verbena* species (Verbenaceae) are traditionally used in many countries to treat diarrhea, fever, gastrointestinal disorders and some sexually transmitted diseases [4]. In addition to antidepressant, ant-jaundice, diuretic, expectorant and anti-influenza effects [5]. Monographs on "Verbenae herba" have been included in the European Pharmacopoeia since 2008, and in the Chinese Pharmacopoeia since 1995 [6].

Numerous *Verbena* species were previously investigated and found to have different flavonoids [4, 7–12], in addition to phenolic acids [13], iridoids [14–19], phenylethanoids [17], phenylpropanoids [18,19] and essential oils [20–24].

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Essential oils of several *Verbena* species were investigated, their chemical composition have been studied [5,20-24] and proved to have anticancer [24] and antimicrobial activities [20,21].

Verbena rigida, known as slender vervain or tuberous vervain, is a flowering herbaceous perennial plant in the family Verbenaceae [25]. It is native to Brazil and Argentina, and grown in temperate climates, as an ornamental plant [26].

The scientific literature on *Verbena rigida* studied its flavonoid content [12] but nothing was found about its essential oil composition and biological activity. The present study was established to evaluate the antimicrobial activity of the essential oil of *Verbena rigida* aerial parts and determine its chemical composition in order to correlate between its chemical composition and potential antimicrobial activity.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Plant material

Aerial parts of *Verbena rigida* Spreng. was collected from the Garden of Faculty of Agriculture, Al-Azhar University, Cairo, Egypt at its flowering stage (April 2020). The plants were kindly, previously, identified by Dr. Adel Okeal, Director of El-Orman Gardens, Giza, Egypt. A voucher herbarium specimen had been deposited in the Department of Pharmacognosy, Faculty of Pharmacy, Cairo University, Cairo, Egypt.

2.2. Preparation of the essential oil

The essential oil was prepared from the fresh aerial parts of *Verbena rigida* (500 g) by hydro distillation using Clevenger-type apparatus. The oil was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and stored in sealed glass vials at 4-6 °C prior to analysis. Percentage yield was determined according to European Pharmacopoeia 2004 [27]

2.3. GC/ MS analysis of the essential oil

The prepared essential oil was subjected to GC/MS analysis using Shimadzu GC//MS – QP 5050 A, fitted with an HP-5 MS capillary column (30 m x 0.25 mm i.d.; 0.25 µm film thickness). Software Class 5000 searched library: Wiley 229 LIB. Carrier gas: Helium (flow rate 1 mL/min). Ionization mode: EL (70 ev). Temperature program: 40 °C (static for 2 min) then gradually increasing at a rate of 2 °C/ min up to 250 °C (static for 8 min). Detector temperature 250 °C. Injector temperature 250 °C.

2.4. Identification of the essential oil

Compounds were identified by comparison of their retention indices (RI), obtained on HP-5 MS column relative to C5-C24 n-alkanes, with those provided in the literature, in addition to Library searched data base Willey 229 LIB and by comparing mass fragmentation patterns with those of the available references and with published data [5,22-24, 28-34].

The percentage composition of the essential oil was determined by computerized peak area measurements. Results were calculated as mean values after three injections of the essential oil and presented in Table 1.

2.5. Test organisms

Pure bacterial strains collected according to American Type Culture Collection (ATCC) were used, Gram +ve: *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 13709, *Staphylococcus epidermidis* ATCC 35984, *Streptococcus pyogenes* ATCC 19615 and *Bacillus subtilis* ATCC 6051, Gram -ve: *Escherichia coli* ATCC 9637, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* ATCC 1705, *Proteus vulgaris* ATCC 8427, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ATCC 27853 and *Shigella boydii* ATCC 9905) as well as pure strains of *Candida albicans* ATCC 10231, *C. glabrata* ATCC 90030, *C. krusei* ATCC 14243 and *C. parapsilosis* ATCC 22019. All micro-organisms were kindly supplied from the Regional Center for Mycology and Biotechnology (RCMB), Al-Azhar University, Cairo, Egypt.

2.6. Testing for antimicrobial activities

Screening of the antimicrobial activity of the essential oil was adopted according to CLSI standards [35], using disc-agar diffusion method [36]. Sterile nutrient agar (Immun präparate, Berlin, D, 26 g agar/L. distilled water) was inoculated with bacterial cells (100 µl of bacterial cell suspension in 25 mL medium) and poured into dishes to give a solid plate. Determination of antimicrobial activities against *Candida* species was achieved by agar-disc diffusion method using

sterile Mueller-Hinton agar (Becton Dickinson, Heidelberg). Ten microlitres of essential oil, dissolved in dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO, Merck, Germany), was applied to sterile paper discs (6 mm diameter) which were placed on the agar surface cultivated with the selected microorganisms. Petri dishes were incubated at 37°C for 24 h in case of bacteria and for 48 h at 30°C in case of *Candida*. Gentamycin (Sigma Aldrich, Steinheim, Germany) and nystatin (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) in concentration range (0.001- 64.00 µg/mL, sterile distilled water) were used as standard antibacterial and antifungal drugs, respectively. DMSO without the essential oil was used as the negative control.

Minimum Inhibitory Concentrations (MICs) were determined using the broth microdilution method [35,36]. Test yeasts or bacteria strains were suspended in media and the cell densities were adjusted to 0.5 McFarland standards at 530 nm wavelength using a spectrophotometric method. Inoculums (0.1 mL) were added to the microtiter plates, which were incubated in a humid atmosphere at 30 °C for 24–48 h (yeast) or at 37 °C for 24 h (bacteria). In addition, positive (medium with inoculums but with no essential oil) and negative (Uninoculated medium, 200 µL) growth controls were prepared. The growth in each well was compared with the growth in the control wells. MICs were visually determined and defined as the lowest concentration of the essential oil produced $\geq 50\%$ growth inhibition for yeast and $\geq 95\%$ growth reduction for bacteria compared with the growth in the control well. Each experiment was performed in triplicate, results were calculated as mean values and presented in Table 2.

2.7. Statistical analysis

Results were expressed as the mean \pm standard deviation; statistical analysis of experimental results were based on the analysis of variance method. Differences were considered statistically significant at the level of $P < 0.05$.

3. Results

3.1. GC-MS analysis of essential oil

The yield of essential oil prepared by hydro-distillation from the aerial parts of *V. rigida* was 0.26 % v/w. The results of GC-MS analysis of the essential oil are presented in table 1, which reports the percentage composition of the essential oil, twenty-eight compounds were detected and identified. The oil is mainly constituted by monoterpenes (91.2%), oxygenated monoterpene compounds constitute 83.7%; isobornyl formate is the main constituent (35.2%) followed by citral (32.9%). Sesquiterpenes constitute 8.8% of oil composition of which 6% are hydrocarbons, predominated by spathulenol (2.5%). This is the first study of the chemical composition of essential oil of *V. rigida*, it differs from reported in literature for other *Verbena* species.

Table 1 Chemical composition of the essential oil of *V. rigida*

No.	KI*	Compound	Formula	Percentage (Mean \pm SD)**
1	936	α -Pinene	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	0.5 \pm 0.0
2	973	Sabinene	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	1.2 \pm 0.0
3	978	β -Pinene	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	1.4 \pm 0.0
4	1016	α -Terpinene	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	0.9 \pm 0.0
5	1041	<i>o</i> -Cymene	C ₁₀ H ₁₄	0.4 \pm 0.0
6	1029	Limonene	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	1.7 \pm 0.0
7	1030	β -Phellandrene	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	1.2 \pm 0.0
8	1033	1,8-Cineole	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ O	4.8 \pm 0.0
9	1086	Terpinolene	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	0.2 \pm 0.0
10	1098	Linalool	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ O	4.5 \pm 0.1
11	1152	Iso-pinocarvone	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ O	0.1 \pm 0.0
12	1163	Pinocarvone	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ O	0.3 \pm 0.0
13	1167	Borneol	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ O	3.7 \pm 0.0
14	1189	α -Terpineol	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ O	0.5 \pm 0.0

15	1228	Isobornyl formate	C ₁₁ H ₁₈ O ₂	35.2 ± 0.1
16	1270	Citral	C ₁₀ H ₁₆ O	32.9 ± 0.0
17	1284	Bornyl acetate	C ₁₂ H ₂₀ O ₂	0.3 ± 0.0
18	1286	Isobornyl acetate	C ₁₂ H ₂₀ O ₂	1.4 ± 0.0
19	1377	α-Copaene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	0.6 ± 0.0
20	1390	β-Elementene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	0.2 ± 0.0
21	1407	Longifolene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	1.4 ± 0.0
22	1418	β-Caryophyllene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	0.9 ± 0.0
23	1424	β-Cedrene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	1.3 ± 0.0
24	1461	Alloaromadendrene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	1.2 ± 0.0
25	1494	Bicyclogermacrene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	0.4 ± 0.0
26	1576	Spathulenol	C ₁₅ H ₂₄ O	2.5 ± 0.0
27	1581	Caryophyllene oxide	C ₁₅ H ₂₄ O	0.2 ± 0.0
28	1633	Iso-spathulenol	C ₁₅ H ₂₄ O	0.1 ± 0.0

* Kovats retention index on HP-5 MS column ** Mean ± standard deviation, (n=3)

In fact, verbenone [22], 1-octen-3-ol [20,22], 2-pentadecanone 6, 10, 14-trimethyl and phytol [20], which were previously detected in the essential oil of *V. officinalis* collected from Iran and *V. bonariensis*, are totally absent in *V. rigida* essential oil under investigation. On the other hand, spathulenol, limonene and 1,8-cineole which were detected in essential oil of *V. rigida* under investigation, have been reported as principal constituents of essential oil of *V. officinalis* from Morocco [23]. Trans-isoelemicin and dihexyl phthalate were undetected in the essential oil of *V. rigida* while trans-isoelemicin was the major component of the volatile constituents in *V. venosa* and dihexyl phthalate was the major component of the volatile constituents in *V. bonariensis*, *V. hybrida* and *V. supine* [5]. Citral and isobornyl formate which are the major constituents in the essential oil of *V. rigida* under investigation, have been previously detected as major constituents of *V. officinalis* from Italy [24].

3.2. Evaluation of antimicrobial activity

Table 2 Antimicrobial activity and MIC of essential oil of *V. rigida*

Microorganism	DD ^a (M ± SD)		MIC ^b (µg/mL)	
	Essential oil	Standard Gentamycin	Essential oil	Standard Gentamycin
Gram +ve Bacteria				
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	19.4 ± 0.4*	24.6 ± 0.5	50	8 × 10 ⁻³
<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>	18.7 ± 0.3*	25.3 ± 0.4	50	1 × 10 ⁻²
<i>Streptococcus pyogenes</i>	12.3 ± 0.2	24.5 ± 0.3	NT	NT
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	17.5 ± 0.5*	26.4 ± 0.4	50	1 × 10 ⁻²
Gram -ve Bacteria		Gentamycin		Gentamycin
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	23.6 ± 0.4*	26.7 ± 0.9	25	8 × 10 ⁻³
<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i>	11.8 ± 0.2	23.7 ± 0.6	NT	NT
<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	12.4 ± 0.1	25.5 ± 0.5	NT	NT
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	19.4 ± 0.2*	22.4 ± 0.3	50	1 × 10 ⁻²
<i>Shigella boydii</i>	12.7 ± 0.2	21.8 ± 0.4	NT	NT

Fungi		Nystatin		Nystatin
<i>Candida albicans</i>	8.6 ± 0.2	15.4 ± 0.1	NT	NT
<i>Candida glabrata</i>	9.2 ± 0.2	16.7 ± 0.4	NT	NT
<i>Candida krusei</i>	10.2 ± 0.1	15.6 ± 0.3	NT	NT
<i>Candida parapsilosis</i>	8.7 ± 0.2	15.8 ± 0.1	NT	NT

DD^a, agar disc diffusion method. Diameter of the inhibition zone (mm) including the disc diameter of 6 mm; MIC^b, minimum inhibitory concentration; values are given as µg/mL; NT, not tested; M ± SD, mean ± standard deviation (n=3). *significant at p < 0.05

Results of evaluation of the antimicrobial activity, obtained from agar disc diffusion method and measurement of MICs, revealed that the essential oil of *V. rigida* exhibits a significant antibacterial activity (Table 2) against Gram +ve bacteria with a remarkable effect on the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis* and *Bacillus subtilis*, with MIC of 50 µg/mL. The essential oil also showed a significant growth inhibitory effect against the Gram -ve bacteria, *E. coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (MIC, 25 and 50 µg/mL, respectively) and no significant antifungal activity against tested species were detected.

4. Discussion

Twenty-six of the detected compounds in the essential oil of *V. rigida* were previously detected in essential oil of *V. officinalis* growing in Italy with different concentrations [24]. The composition of the essential oil is greatly different than the previously reported in *V. officinalis* growing either in Iran or Morocco [22,23], and differs than the composition of essential oil of *V. bonariensis* which contains 21 components, from which only terpineol is detected in *V. rigida* [20]. Also, the composition of the essential oil of *V. rigida* have been proved to be totally different than several other *Verbena* species collected from Egypt [5]. The difference in composition is most likely attributed to climate, soil composition, altitude and age as well as species variation [37].

The antimicrobial activity of the major compounds of the investigated oil has been previously well defined by several researchers. The oil components, namely limonene [38], linalool [38,39], borneol [38,40], α-terpineol [38], citral [38,21], 1,8-cineole [41] α-pinene and β-pinene [42] have been reported to display antibacterial activity against several bacterial species.

The presence of these compounds in the essential oil of *V. rigida* may account for its observed antimicrobial activity.

The results of this study on the chemical composition and antimicrobial activity of *V. rigida* essential oil are the first to be reported. These findings support the observations of some other researchers which proved that essential oil of *V. bonariensis* showed inhibitory activity against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (50%) and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (22%) growth but with no activity against *Escherichia coli* [20].

5. Conclusion

In this study, the chemical composition and the antimicrobial activity of the essential oil of aerial parts of *V. rigida* were investigated for the first time. The oil is rich in oxygenated monoterpene constituents especially isobornyl formate and citral and showed significant *in vitro* antibacterial activity against tested microorganisms. Further *in vivo* studies are needed to ensure the antibacterial activity and possible use of the essential oil of *V. rigida* as an antimicrobial agent.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The author declares no conflict of interest.

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